

Impact of Islamic Finance on Agribusiness and SMEs Growth

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Abstract

The primary issue facing Pakistan's agricultural sector is inadequate access to finance. The study seeks to examine the effect of Islamic finance on Agribusiness and SME growth on the profitability of various modes used by Islamic banks. This research consists on one research question, three objectives. It utilizes quarterly data Islamic banking statistic from 2008 until 2019. The study based on secondary data, and this study is quantitative. Data gathered systematically to answers the research question which acquired from secondary sources such as the financial statements of Islamic banking with different sector of SMEs and Agribusiness. Data for this study collected from SBP websites of Islamic banking bulletin and different SMEs sector of Pakistan. Furthermore, the software SPSS EVIEWS has been used for data analysis. This study conducts linear regression and Durbin Watson method test results for the evaluation and analysis of data. And Unit root diagnostics test of appropriate result. The finding reveals that best Islamic mode for loaning agribusiness and SMEs. Besides, AGRI profit and SMEs profit Performing Financing influence to agricultural financing significantly growth of Islamic finance for agribusiness and growth for SMEs trend are show in this research, applying Shariah rules. Therefore financing must be considered to given fully support to SMEs communities they can get easy business capital access. This research encourages Islamic banking professionals to pay more attention to farmers in Pakistan with Islamic financing. Finding for this study recommends enhancing the competency of Islamic finance tools in the agricultural sector as well as improving Islamic funding policy instruments.

Keywords: Islamic Bank, Agri Profit, Islamic Finance, Agri- Business.

I. INTRODUCTION AND CONTEXT

Nowadays, agriculture is playing a key role in one of the main contributors to (GDP) Gross Domestic Product of most of the countries. (SBP) State Bank of Pakistan characterized the Islamic banking in consonance the code and worth

arrangement of Islam and represented the regular great administration and hazard the executives rules, by the standards set somewhere around Islamic Sharia'h. Islam is characterizes Allah Almighty with no condition as total convenience. It is a complete code of life which includes on the bearings of Allah Almighty and the actions of the Holy Prophet Muhammad (Peace be upon him).

Islamic banking is known as new corporate Islamic finance or Islamic fund or Shariah-agreeable account is categorized as money related basis representation a wide range of banking administrations with Shariah law and it works usually in the Islamic economies. The most important significant for Islamic finance is that all exchanges must be led vial-narrows (trade contract) instead of through al-riba (financing cost based obligation contract). There is a few mode of Islamic finance that interface Islamic bank saves money with their clients. The agreements that are utilized by waves which have social objectives that are important as making profits.(2007, Hanif&Hudaib; 2019, Zafar &Sulaiman).

The Islamic banking development growth in the worldwide market has been exceptionally promising to comply with moral and strict principles (Bukhari et al., 2014). Imaginative items and managements of Islamic banking had been broadly discovered by (Mbawuni and Nimako, 2017 Hamza, (2016); these include: Mudarabah (Profit and Misfortune Sharing), Wadiah (protection), Musharaka (joint venture), Murabahah (cost in addition), and Ijara (rental) are a few parts of Islamic banking.

A. MUDARABAH

It is an Islamic contract where one side supplies cash while other provides an opportunity of the administration to attempt a specific trade. The meeting that provides the capital is called the capital owner and the other party is added as a professional who really manages the business. Mudarabah is also called benefit sharing in view of the fact that a proportion is shared in the form of funding benefits and the investor is

not guaranteed an arrival and carries the risk of misfortune. Schaik, D., according to Schaik. "(2001) Mudarabah is a benefit sharing understanding agreement in which a bank provides the absolute capital required to fund a company the customer gives the ability to executives and work.

B. MURABAH

Murabaha is also called expense in addition to financing or cost-in addition to deal. In this method of financing the acquisition of benefit financed for overall revenue. To begin with the benefit is bought for customer or client and afterward exchanged at foreordained cost. Installment could be in singular amount or in portions and responsibility for resource stays with bank till full installments are made. However, Murabah financing relies on the law of an increase (or cost in addition to) in which a bank is allowed to buy products for a customer and exchange them with the customer at a pre-decided cost that includes the first expense in addition to the net sales arranged. Thus, in working capital and trade funding this agreement is widely used. (Suleiman, 2000)

C. MUSHARAKAH (Partnership)

Musharakah is joint venture or association structure with benefit and sharing loss that utilized in Islamic fund rather than enthusiasm bearing advances. Each gathering engaged with business allows Musharakah to participate in the benefits and dangers. Contracts are like joint enterprise understandings in which a bank and business imaginative contribute money and work with a business venture. Besides, any benefit and misfortune from the venture is part taken in a pre-decided way. (Alam, 2003).

D. IJARA

Ijara is commonly used by Islamic banks to fund buyer items equipment and vehicles, financing home. It has also discovered its way to venture and transportation financing in resource-based financing in bigger and increasingly complex exchange. They are the operational or budgetary leasing contracts.

E. ISTISNA (CONSTRUCTION MANUFACTURING)

Istisna contracts depend on the idea of dispatched or agreement constructing where a gathering attempts to create a particular useful for future conveyance at a pre-decided cost. It may be utilized in the financing of produced merchandise development and framework projects. Above all instruments depend on the standard of riba (interest) prevention all try to keep up Islamic business morals.

F. SALAM

Salam implies an agreement where in advance installment is made for products to be conveyed at future date. It is fundamental nature were expected to be acquired is completely determined leaving no doubt prompting question. Bai Salam covers nearly everything which is equipped for being certainly described as to amount quality and workmanship. SALAM is perfect for horticulture financing that can utilize to fund working capital needs of the clients. The possibility of Salam is a special case to general guideline that forbids forward deal. (Zaabi, 2010).

G. WORLD WIDE ASPECTS OF ISLAMIC BANKING

Nowadays, Islamic banking has expanded quickly on the globe specially in Muslim countries as well as in non-Muslim country for example, the United Kingdom where Islamic Bank of Britain is operating. The Islamic Finance Development Report shows that year-on-year the global Islamic finance industry is fastly growing by 11% to US\$ 2.4 trillion in assets in 2017 or 6% of CAGR growth in 2012, based on figures published for 56 countries frequently in the Middle East and South and South East Asia. However, in terms of assets, Iran, Saudi Arabia and Malaysia remain the largest Islamic financial markets with Cyprus, Nigeria and Australia experiencing the fastest growth. The 131 countries evaluated for Islamic finance have once again been led by Malaysia, Bahrain and the UAE. (IFDIS, 2018).

I. ISLAMIC BANKING IN PAKISTAN

The capital of the Islamic financial industry increased by Rs. 202 billion by 7.3 percent in the quarter from April to June 2019 and stayed at Rs. 2.992 billion by 30 June 2019. Islamic financial industry stores have also achieved 9.8 percent growth of Rs. 216 billion and Rs. 2.415 billion by the end of June 2019. By the end of June 2019, the

share of Islamic financial resources and stores in the general financial sector was reported at 14.4% and 15.9% individually. By the end of June 2019, the profit before the Islamic financial industries evaluation was recorded at Rs. 32 billion. By the end of June 2019, 22 Islamic financial organizations, 5 undeniable Islamic banks and 17 regular banks with independent Islamic financial branches were part of the Islamic financial sector system. The Islamic financial industry branch system was registered at 2,913 (broadcast across 113 regions) by the end of June 2019. More than 77% of the branches had moved to Punjab and Sindh. Thus, the number of Islamic financial windows used by traditional banks with Islamic independent financial branches remained at 1,348. (IBB: April-June, 2019)

J. AGRIBUSINESS IN PAKITAN

The agricultural sector of Pakistan plays a key role in the economy by contributing 18.9% of GDP and maintaining 42.3% of the workforce. It is also a major source of remote trade revenue and promotes development in various segments. The administration focuses on promoting small and under-estimated framers and promoting innovative technologies on a small scale to advance the production of agricultural products. (PES 2017-18).

During 2017-18 the reported horticulture area marked a 3.81% growth capability and achieved its 3.5 percent development focused and 2.07 percent growth of an Agro year. Kharif is the first season of crop growth from April to June and harvested between October and December. In which Rice, sugarcane, Cotton, Maize, Moong, Mash, Bajra and jowar are Kharif crops .Rabi starts in October-December and is harvested in April-May the second sowing season. Wheat, gram, lentil (masoor), tobacco, rapseed, barley and mustard are Rabi crops.

The agricultural production of Pakistan depends on timely availability of water. According to the Corporate Statistical Database of the Food and Agriculture Organization Pakistan is among the top fifteen producers of cotton, rice, mango, apricot, sugarcane, chickpea, beef, broccoli, oranges, wheat, pulses, cauliflower, milk and onion. (FAOSTAT, 2016). Abdullah, D. Z. (2015) states that Pakistan is furnished and rich in natural resources including best range of seasons,

Rivers, Mountains, vast irrigation system, Lakes, and cultivated agricultural sector.

In addition to this, Arshad, (2005) there are numerous variables that slow down the advancement of agribusiness area in this nation absence of member, absence of land to be planted with crops opposition towards new innovation and method and absence of capital. Further, (Asad, 2011) pointed out that the example of this cultivation sector must be understood in briefing on how to understand land owner bank financing. For example, the salary of farmers and visionaries of agricultural businesses is not quite the same as the pay examples of various business exercises that can be received occasionally. The farmer has earned the harvest time.

The financial service for small and medium enterprises engaged in agricultural production (i.e. agriculture) and production-related activities such as supply of inputs, manufacturing, trade, wholesale and marketing at all levels, is specified as SBP by agricultural (SMEs) Small and Medium Enterprises. Agribusiness is engaging since independence to develop in economy of Pakistan. In the early time it become dominant sector but now a day due to unconditional political issue, social, environmental and climate condition effect the performance its production yield goes down day by day.

In addition to this, for running their business efficiently, the farming community needs money to cover its regular expenses and financing. Islamic agricultural financing aimed at smallholder farmers. However, the products of Islamic bank such as Murabaha and Mudarabah drawn sustainable interest from Pakistani religious citizen. Globally, Mudarabha & Murabaha products are fastest growing instrument with study conclusion of many author according to customer's awareness and satisfaction towards Islamic banking system increase day by day. Accordingly, World Islamic Financial report, the assets of 1.34 trillion are being managed according to Islamic investment principles while 20% of banking customers now moved towards Islamic financial products. (Dar & Azmi, 2012).

Zabbai (2010) stated that Salam contract is used by small farmer easily support for this. In Salam contract farmer will get fund to purchase seeds,

fertilizer and other materials to grow crop and able to pay workers if any.

According to Pakistan Economy Survey report Pakistan has negative impact on agriculture performance and showing agricultural up to fit an expanding exchange shortfall. Because of diminishing harvest creation the dependence on the import of agro nourishment things is expanding along these lines squeezing outside trade holds. Resultantly, the exchange deficiency of Pakistan has crumbled during most recent few years. Survey, P. E. (2017-2018).

II. PROBLEM STATEMENT

One of the most hard hit entities of global financial crises of 2008 included small and medium enterprises (SMEs) on account of their fragile financial structure, small risk cushion and the fact that even incurring losses could not exempt them from paying interest liabilities. This has led the institutions to seek an alternative (parallel) banking and financial system such as Islamic financing. Therefore, it is pertinent to understand the impact of Islamic financial services on the growth and profitability of SMEs with special emphasis on Agribusinesses in Pakistan which is a sector with limited research despite having critical importance given agriculture sector's contribution in economy.

III. RESEARCH QUESTION

How does Islamic finance impact on Agribusiness and SME's?

IV. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To study Islamic finance concentration modes on different sectors of business.
- To measure the growth in volume of Agribusiness and SMEs with the finance from Islamic Financial Institutes.
- To measure Islamic finance impact on Agribusiness and SMEs in term of Profitability.

V. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. ISLAMIC FINANCING

Islamic financing approaches have been classified into two methods by Hanif and Iqbal (2010); (1) what more, shariah-agreeable goods. (2) Shariah-focused exchanges. Shariah appropriate items are defined as a method of Islamic account where

agent return is predictable and set out in Shariah law, which includes Murabahah (cost in addition to benefit deal or increase funding), Bai Bithaman Ajil (protection of benefit deal), Ijarah (a rental understanding) Musharakah (decreasing the lodging fund or Musharakah), Bai Salam (future transportation of goods), Istisna (securing products by detail, where costs are paid in advance) and Qard Hassan (securing products by detail, where costs are paid in advance) (free credit). Shariah-based exchanges, however, are a form of finance that takes into account benefit requirement so outcome of the venture, taking into account the principles of benefit sharing where the arrival of the agent is not set in advance. The two benefit sharing courses of action or partnership contracts preferred under Islamic law are Mudarabah (benefit sharing) and Musharakah (organization financing).

According to Abidin, I. S (2018), Profits/losses are allocated in fixed percentages between the bank and other partners as stated in Musharaka contract. A part of the investment is provided by the Islamic Bank which alternates with other sources of finance for the enterprise.(Zabbai, 2010) stated that the Salam contract is easily used for this by small farmers who support it. Thus, in the Salam contract farmers would obtain funds to buy seeds, fertilizer and other materials to grow their crops.

Mohammed, A. I., Ogunbado, A. F., & Bashir, A (2016) defined that Salam contract is type of advance payment for particular products which can delivered to the bank at a specified future date and palace. Besides, (Saiti, 2018) indicated that Salam contract which is used by the Islamic Bank for the financing of utility products and for agricultural purposes. Further, Ijarah is another common contract used by Islamic banks as (Billah, 2019) defined it as a lease-to-purchase agreement.

Hussein & Mat, (2019) & Lahsasna et al., (2018) suggested that Ijarah contract take different forms which include Sukuk Ijarah, regular Ijarah and Al-Ijarah Al-Muntahiyah bi Al-Tamlik. Lewis and Algaoud (2001) states that there are five religious features that specific character of Islamic finance for instance riba (intrigue), haram (prohibited) or halal (worthy), gharar (hypothetical) or maysir (gaming), zakat (the embraced separating philanthropy) and Shariah (Islamic) board.

Mirakhor and Iqbal (2011) point out that division between Islamic economic structures with the customary framework includes: Firstly, Islamic monetary framework makes progress toward impartial, reasonable society and financial order. The prevention of interest (riba) in the Islamic finance related framework is proposed to maintain a strategic distance from exploiting through control costs and to ensure borrower. Secondly, the rule of cooperation is focus of the Islamic monetary system. This is proven by the risk taking, profit and loss sharing structure that promotes the effectiveness of the business adventure as opposed to the reliability of the business individual of the usual monetary system. Thirdly, Islamic fund is the exacting moral criteria of Islamic law or Shariah.

Bukhari, Huma, Imam, and Qadri, (2014) stated that Islamic banking development in the global economy has been extraordinarily commitment to the standards moral and strict values. Imam and Kodar (2015) provided proofs in their academic work suggesting that despite its moderately little size contrasted with the general size of the money related framework, Islamic banking to be sure adds to the financial development.

According to Janahi et al. (2017), customers' fulfillment had been seen as real factor of Islamic banking and had been mostly discovered. Naceur et al., (2015) demonstrate that nowadays, Islamic Banking is adding to more inclusion in the market of credit by explicitly researching the role of Islamic banking in advancement of SMEs lending.

Leaman (2015) maintained that likewise contends that Islamic banking is required to be something other than a business establishment in light of sharia rules that precludes to focus without anyone else organizations, yet in addition to focus on social duty. The suggestion is that Islamic banking must keep up the equalization of advantages picked up among establishments and society. Butt, Naveed & Ahmed (2018) also highlighted that Islamic banking has developed different agreements for their customer which are used in Islamic banking for the purpose of financing to their customers according to Islamic law. These are: 1) Murabaha 2) Mudaraba 3) Ijarah and 4) Musharakah.

The Pakistani market in recent years is a huge market of opportunity for Islamic banking,

according to (Khan, Ahmed, Rahman & Haleem, 2018). Furthermore, due to introduction of unique marketing strategies to establish and maintain relationships with their clients for long-term corporate survival and growth Islamic banks develop relationships with their clients. Islamic banks sell to customer's products and services under the same category such as savings accounts, current accounts, credit cards, home financing and other products and services (Amin et al., 2017).

Saleem, M. Yusuf (2013) pointed out that there are different business contracts offered by Islamic banking is accepted have an option to improve the state of society particularly in the financial field and ready the cause of individuals to understand its advantages as the objective of maqasid shariah. Also, Asutay (2014) stated that the establishment of Islamic (account) is the lesson of Islamic financial matters to be a restriction on usury (premium), yet additionally identified with the issue of financial improvement.

Islamic banking is a definition of monetary assurance for the budgetary division as a major aspect of the Islamic financial concept. The benefit course based on the standard of equity and worth. It is further added by Askari, Iqbal and Mirakhor (2015) that social and monetary equity is the development of Islamic financial system. Moreover as mentioned above Islamic finance, which relies on Islamic law also has the responsibility to consider the benefits of individuals.

V. J. Sadeghi *et al.*, (2017) stated that the reason for Islamic banking is to finance exercises that are administered by the principle of the Islamic standard and basically forecast installments and get premiums. P. P. Biancone *et al.*, (2018) stated that Shariah standards have essential idea that God is the proprietor of the entire world just as the entire resources. Muslims reserve the privilege to make their wealth giving that it is acknowledged or put resources into a way that is following to Sharia standards.

Abidin and Haseeb, (2018) argued that Islamic banks were set up in a similarly short period of time by capturing a good market share and competing with their competitors. Moreover, Nizar S.M.R. (2015) explained that Islamic banking as part of the Islamic financial system is regarded with an expansive point of view

generated part of the global budgetary market multiplies in all parts of the globe.

Basheer et al. (2018) argued that Islamic banks were set up in a similarly short period of time by capturing a good market share and competing with their competitors. Haseeb (2018) also argued that over the past 10 years the Islamic banking and financial services industry has seen rapid growth along with a competent turning point reaching towards more than \$2 trillion by 2015.

In addition, Islamic bank was described by Al-Jarhi and Iqbal (2001) as a financial base performing all standard financial practices including interest-free obtaining and loaning. It unlocks Mudarabah or Wakalah-based assets and can accept application stores as interest-free credit. Besides, Dar and Azmi (2012) pointed out that the study conclusion of several authors that includes Murabaha and Mudarabah products are the fastly growing around the world is increasing day by day according to the awareness and satisfaction of customers with the Islamic banking system. Moreover, 1.34 trillion assets are managed according to Islamic investment principles according to the World Islamic Financial Report while 20 percent are handled according to Islamic investment principles.

In compliance P. P. Biancone and M. Radwan (2019) that according to Sharia law Islamic financial instruments should completely implement the Sharia instructions.

B. AGRIBUSINESS

The Islamic agricultural finance system seeks to comply with main Shariah requirements. The prohibition of Riba and the prohibition of excessive Gharara are the two most critical and applicable principles SBP (2019).

In (2013) Ridhwan, Aziz and Yusoff, and Shafiai, in (2017) stated that it is not easy to grow the agricultural industry because farmers face a lot of risk issues in their agricultural chain. Moreover, the risk consists of production risk, technical risk, risk of pests and diseases, risk of price fluctuation or market risk varies, risk of changes in government policy and financial risk, risk of climate change becomes the source of uncertainty due to all this risk.

Asaad, (2011) pointed out that there is a problem facing by farmers related uncontrolled nature risks

different reason of crop fluctuates so bank is intermediary for profit loss sharing system having no interest rate based system. On the other hand, Khasanahet *al.*, (2013) claimed that the risk-sharing theory of principle for farmers who often face the risk of farming. Benefit Loss Sharing model banks and farmers in Islamic banks share their income and losses according to banking policy.

Bardhan, P., and Mookherjee, D. (2011) maintained that the achievement of farmer can be seen from effecting of agrarian development. Hence, the farming development described by an expansion in agrarian creation, expanded editing power, fast spread of seeds and expanded income of framer.

Ahmed *et al.*, 2012 Briefing that A few landowners don't have solid funding to back the entirety of their farming venture exercises until gather time shows up. The yield from last year is one of the key wellsprings of capital. For the most part, farmers need to deliver harvests as quickly as time allows raising cash, so crops need to be sold at a low cost on a regular basis. Moreover farmers don't acquire enough cash either for family unit utilization or to build the measure of agrarian creation.

Haqetal., (2013) defined sufficiency in formal rural credit difficult access to formal credit, high loan rates costly information sources, lack of water system water and long-standing growth strategies are the key considerations responsible for the framer and low performance demonstration of agriculture.

Wagan et al. (2016) suggested that Loans to farmers have shown that they can build up the pay and desires of farmers for daily comforts. Banks need to understand the concept of agrarian business prior to selecting the best financing item for landowners. This nature influences the actions associated with farmers' income. Coleman (2006) The Agriculture sector in case of small farmer have not been attractive in their financial institution which have been unwilling to issue loans because of their failure security high transaction cost and higher default risk which is linked by small loans.

Muhammad Ridhwan Ab. Aziz (2010) claimed that Agro Bank is only a bank that intensively provides financing facilities and funds to farmers

and agricultural entrepreneurs although some of products provided are not yet with Shariah complaint. Dr. Muhammad Fauzi Jumingan, (2008) maintained that Islam stated that there are three core principles of agriculture;

1) Islam encourages people to participate in agriculture because it is the best way to reap strong benefits (thawab) from this while earning beneficial and halal income.

2) Islam encourages the selling of agro-products, but forbids any form of business fraud or monopoly.

3) However according to Islam discourages all farming practices for questionable invalid purposes such as planting grapes for the production of grapes.

Asad (2011) stated that to understand a financing item for landowner banks clarify the example of this cultivating business must understand. The example of farmers and farming business visionaries earning salaries is not exactly the same as the pay examples of various business exercises that can sometimes earn. These farmer earned their money in the time of harvesting. Abdullah, Khan, Jebran, and Ali, (2015) stated that Pakistan is furnished and rich in natural resources, including the best seasonal range, rivers, mountains, extensive irrigation systems, lakes, and cultivated agriculture.

VI. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The main objective revolves around assessing the influence and profitability of Islamic finance on Pakistan's agribusiness and other SME sectors and which Islamic mode is mostly preferred for Agribusiness SME's. To achieve this statistical approach has been employed to observe results. This methodology includes quantitative analysis, where the secondary data has been collected through the official website of State Bank of Pakistan. However, this method is frequently used to analyze study variables through using particular techniques.

Figure 1: Research Flowchart

A. Sample

The sample of different (SMEs) Small and Mid size Enterprises of Pakistan including Agribusiness has been used. It includes listed business sector and companies registered with State Bank of Pakistan at the time period of 2008-2019. However, (SMEs) Small and Medium Enterprises include 11 different sectors and different Islamic modes observations semiannually is used over the period 2008 to 2019.

B. Data Collection

For the study, monthly time series data from 2008 to 2019 will be used. In order to obtain statistically accurate results, diagnostic tests will be carried out before the study. The research methodology for this unique analysis, the application of data collection and sampling techniques measures of all variables along with brief explanations of how the data will be evaluated and screened and the reliability analysis methods selected, regression analysis and correlation techniques, fitness test, Unit root test, R square, and statistics through Durbin Watson. The collected data was analyzed through (SPSS) Statistical Package for Social Sciences and Eviews to evaluate quantitative data analysis to depict results.

B. EMPIRICAL MODEL

An empirical model of this study is:

A linear regression model is constructed with two independent variables, βx^1 and βx^2 , representing the regression model parameters, and ε , the disturbance error term. The Linear Regression equation is shown below:

$$y = \alpha + \beta x^1 + \beta x^2 \dots \dots \varepsilon$$

: - **SME Profit** = $\alpha + (\text{SME Profit})_{t-1} + \text{Islamic finance..}$

C. UNIT ROOT

Unit root test known as fix test, since it is a test whether or not a specific coefficient of an autoregressive model has an estimate of one. If the information of test is not fixed, the next stage to test the mix

level at that point. Fixed methods for deciding whether the information has been fixed by contrasting the quality of the PP statistical regression coefficients with the basic estimation of the measurable appropriation (Widarjono, 2016).

D. LEAST SQUARE REGRESSION

The least square method is a form of mathematical regression analysis used to decide the best fit line for a data set providing a visual demonstration of the relationship between data points. Each data point represents the relationship between known independent variable and an unknown dependent variable. The most common use of this method is linear or ordinary to create a straight line that minimizes the sum of the error squares generated by the results. The method of regression analysis starts with a set of data points to be plotted on the x-and y-axis graphs. An analyst using the least square method will create a line of best fit that explains the potential relationship between independent and dependent variables. In regression analysis, the dependent variables are shown on the vertical axis, while the independent variables are shown on the horizontal axis.

E. DURBIN WATSON METHOD

A residual autocorrelation test from a statistical regression study is the Durbin Watson statistic. There will always be a value (0 to 4) in the Durbin-Watson statistics. A 2.0 indicates that the sample has not observed any autocorrelation. Positive autocorrelation is indicated by values from 0 to 2 and negative autocorrelation is indicated by values from 2 to 4.

F. VARIABLES MEASUREMENT

This research focuses on what are characteristics determinants of Islamic finance in Pakistan in Agribusiness. This research consists of different variables. Independent variables comprising growth in term of Net profit and dependent variable is an Agribusiness profit and SMES profit

G. INDEPENDENT VARIABLE

NET PROFIT

The actual profit after working expenses not included in the calculation of gross profit have been paid. Net profit equal how much

profit is generated from revenue. Net income is also called the bottom line for a company.

VII. RESULTS & FINDINGS

A. Discussion

The data reveals the fact that objectives of study were analyzed through statistical tools and techniques. The discussion in detail will highlight key objectives of proposed study and more importantly data results of 12 years of previous data of State Bank of Pakistan that will help in observing results.

After collection of systematically data from State Bank of Pakistan from 2008 to 2019 regarding Islamic Banking Reports for the various (SMEs) Small and Medium Business Enterprises and agribusiness industries. However, data analysis was carried out by using (SPSS) Special Package for Social Sciences and Eviews. Linear regression and the results of the Durbin Watson Test method has been applied to observed results related to study objectives. ADF test has also been conducted to observe probability value.

The study aimed to investigate the effect of Islamic finance on Agribusiness and the growth of small and medium-sized enterprises on the profitability of the different Islamic banking sectors used by Islamic banks. This analysis focuses on secondary data and is a quantitative review. Systematically collected data from 2008 to 2019 respond to research issue from secondary sources, For example Islamic banking reports for the various SMEs and agribusiness industries. For data processing work on SPSS and Eviews. This research consists of one research issue, three objectives. This study used linear regression and the results of the Durbin Watson test method to evaluate and analyze data. Thus, the ADF test showed a probability value of 0.00 to 0.004 which shows a P value of less than 5 % which means that the null hypothesis is rejected and there is a unit root.

The independent variables (Agri-profit and SME-profit) were analyzed to understand the significant profitability of Islamic loans. The coefficient value of Agri-Islamic profit is (2.92) which does not have positive effect on production and also increases the probability with a standard value of 0.5 which is a positive effect on this production

(0.2562), Agri-Islamic loan with a coefficient (0.010000) implies an increase of 1% (0.01) of the contribution to the agribusiness loan. The probability result of the Agri Islamic loan is (0.0480), which is fine. Adjusted R-Square is 0.8600 or 86.0%. Durbin Watson's statistics demonstrates the result value of 2.1 that shows no auto-correlation. Adjusted R-square (0.780000), Prop(F-statist) which is 0.000. These all are values that show a significant result.

The coefficient value of SMEs profit is (-5.03E-15) have negative impact which is not good effect for this output and also SMEs profit T Statistic show the negative value impact (-3.026886), Probability increase with the standard value of 0.5 which is (0.0051). SMEs loan which coefficient is (0.050600) means 5% increase (0.05) contribution in SMEs loan and T Statistic value impact (4.60E+14), SMEs Islamic loan probability result is (0.0476) which is valid. The amount of Adjusted R-Square is 0.7800 or 78.0%. Durbin Watson stat Show the result value of (2.320212) which shows no auto-correlation occurs. Adjusted R-square (0.690000), Prop(F-statistic) which is 0.000. These all values show a significant value.

Finally, the study showed a statistically significant positive as well as negative relationship between AGRIPROFIT and SMEs profiting from ISLAMIC finance in Pakistan. Islamic banking therefore increases its performance and profit by improving Islamic liquidity policy and policy performance. From the result it concluded that in Oder to achieve higher profitability the Islamic banking should make use of current financing policies at the ordinary level.

OBJECTIVE # 1: TO STUDY ISLAMIC FINANCE CONCENTRATION ON DIFFERENT SECTORS OF BUSINESS.

Volume of Different Financing Instruments

Figure 2: Volume of different financing instrument

In figure 2 Discuss about the total contribution of different mode of Islamic finance **from 2008 to 2019 years**. After the sum of all modes following above figure are in this pie chart which shows different volume of percentage of different financial instrument. The data are collected secondary from State bank website which gives different figure of Islamic modes. In above figure 4.1 shows contribution of Murahaba 3898.32 billion (35%), Ijaraha mode contributed 1143.59 billion (10%), Musharaka mode contribute 676.93 billion (6%), Dimishing Musharkha contribute 3583.4 billion (32%), Salam 355.12 billion (3%), Istisna 653.8 billion (6%) and others mode of Islamic finance contributed in different SMEs and Agribusiness is 752.97 billion (7%). From above result. Murahaba contribution is more than other mode and second is Dimishing Musharkha this mode of Islamic finance shows high volume in financial instruments. In Pakistan's Islamic banking system the popular mode of financing Murabahah because technically "the Diminishing Musharakah is not a pure form of Musharakah but a mixture of Ijarah, Murabahah and Musharakah.

In Pakistan's Islamic banking business in other Islamic banking markets issue of Murabah-based financing also prevails reflecting the capitalist thinking of banking. In Pakistan's Islamic banking system has completely neglected the Qard-e-Hasana instrument, the social welfare instrument of Islamic financing. Cebeci, "2012),

A. PERCENTAGE SHARE OF DIFFERENT INDUSTRIES OPT FOR ISLAMIC FINANCE

Figure 3: Percentage share of different industries for Islamic Finance

In above figure 3 Show the percentage of different sector which contributed in Islamic finance.

In above table total eleven different sectors show their contribution. Agribusiness 2.5965(6%), Cement 2.236(5%), Shoe and leather garments 9.575(21%), Electrical appliance 0.455 (1%), Individual 3.338(7%), Chemical and pharmacy 1.365(3%), Textile 5.255(12%), Sugar 1.049(2%), Financial 0.73(2%), Production and transmission of energy 4.259(10%), and others 13.697(31%). The 68% of the population of Pakistan is connected with agricultural sector growing in economy. The growth of SMEs sector has been foreseen by Pakistan while 95% of SMEs not survive in the first year of their inception. It is also surprising that Pakistan's Islamic banking sector has also strongly ignored the small and medium-sized enterprises sector. (Mubarik Govindaraju & Devadason 2016).

B. TREND OF SMES AND AGRICULTURE FINANCE WITH ISLAMIC FINANCE INSTRUMENTS

Figure 4: Trend of SMEs and Agriculture finance with Islamic finance instruments

In above figure 4 data of every year used for result. This graph discusses about the trend of SMEs and Agriculture finance with Islamic finance instruments with the time its changes/ fluctuates. This is linear relationship between finance percentage verse times in (years). The data which has been analyzed which range from 2008 to 2018 where the month remains same throughout the trend of SMEs and Agribusiness which is end of every year December. The curve which is drawn by linear relationship between finance verse times has a resulted which is shown as a linear dotted line that passes in between throughout the curve.

C. TREND OF SMES FINANCE WITH ISLAMIC INSTRUMENT

The Trend of SMEs starts from (approximately) 9.9% in December 2008 and end with 6.9% in December 2018. Its start from high percentage with passage of time it fallen down with different financial crisis some change occurs by government in different policy of SMEs business.

D. TREND OF AGRICULTURAL WITH ISLAMIC INSTRUMENT

The trend in agricultural finance starts at 0% in 2008 and remains consistent at 0% until December 2010. In the early years, it is difficult for the agricultural sector to gain knowledge of the Islamic instrument that is best for Agribusiness, but the turbulence started in 2010 and ended with 4 per cent. The parallel point between the results of SMEs and Agricultural finance is 5.5%.

However, the financial performance data from Islamic Banking Statistics for the period between December 2008 and December 2018 are turbulence in the starting years, rising to 0 percent and ending at 4 percent.

OBJECTIVE-02:TO MEASURE THE GROWTH IN VOLUME OF SMES WITH THE FINANCE FROM ISLAMIC FINANCIAL INSTITUTES. (TO MEASURE THE GROWTH OF ISLAMIC FINANCE FOR SMES AND AGRIBUSINESS)

Growth of Islamic Finance for SMEs

Figure 5: Growth of Islamic Finance for SMEs

This is a linear relationship between the growth of Islamic finance for small and medium-sized enterprises and a line chart drawn between the percentages of growth of Islamic finance in terms of time. The resultant starts from-9 per cent in December 2008 and flows linearly to-5 percent in December 2017.

A) GROWTH OF ISLAMIC FINANCE FOR AGRIBUSINESS

Figure 6: Growth of Islamic finance for Agribusiness

This is linear relationship between Islamic finance for agribusiness from growth. This is linear graph between growth percentage verse times. The maximum value the range of 2009 to 2018 was observed to be has 85% from March 2009 to March 2018.

OBJECTIVE # 03TO MEASURE ISLAMIC FINANCE IMPACT ON SMES AND AGRIBUSINESS GROWTH IN TERM OF NET PROFIT

The Augmented dickey fuller (ADF) test is used in this study to examine the stationary behavior of the market structure and performance models of Islamic banking. The empirical results of the ADF test for each variable in levels are shown in Table A.

Variable	Unit Root Test (ADF)	P-Value
Agribusiness Islamic Finance	-7.768525 (Level)	0.000
Agribusiness Islamic Finance Growth	-3.888075 (Level)	0.000
Agribusiness Profitability	-7.879515 (Level)	0.001
SME Islamic Finance	-5.279057 (Level)	0.004
SMEs Islamic Finance Growth	-7.275328 (Level)	0.004
SME Profitability	-5.381067 (Level)	0.001

Table 1:Estimated parameters of the multiple linear regression model by using the method of least squares.

There are two variables: **AGRIBUSSINESS** and **SMEs**. These variables are based on three factors, **Islamic finance, Islamic growth and profitability.**

In Table 1 All variables are not stationary at the current level when the level of significance is 5%.The standard ADF and PP test to check the order of integration of these variable. (Abidin et al.,2015).Since which variables are not stationary it is necessary to proceed with the unit root test at the level of the first degree of integration (First Difference) which is the value of variable statistics PP is higher than the critical value and data has been stationary at $p < 0.05$ on the degree of integration and can be proceed to the next co-integration test. The principle for Error Correction Model continuity remains between

economic variables over the long term. There discontinuity in one period in the short term the Error Correction Model will correction next period. (De-Graft Acquah, 2015).

B) DEPENDENT VARIABLE: AGRIPROFIT

Method: Least

Date: 06/24/20

Sample (adjusted) 2

Included observations: 53 after

Variable	Coefficien	Std.	t-	Prob.
Cr	t	Error	Statistic	
C	0.000000	4.76E-17	0.00000	1.000
AGRI PROF	2.92E-17	2.54E-17	1.14861	0.256
IT (-1)			1	2
AGRI ISLA	0.01	2.29E-19	3.93E+1	0.048
M LOAN			6	0
R-squared	0.86	Mean dependent var	0.705	821
Adjusted R-squared	0.78	S.D. dependent var	1.579	409
S.E. of regression	2.89E-16	Sum squared resid	4.18E	-30
F-statistic	7.77E+32	Durbin-Watson stat	2.185	835
Prob(F-statistic)	0			

Table 2: Estimated parameters of the simple linear regression model by using the method of least squares.

In table 2 diagnostics test of unit root and autocorrelation are analyzed. The independent variable is used for the same dependent lag (AGRI ISLAIMC LOAN) profit of the previous year. Estimated parameters of the multiple linear regression model by using the method of least squares.

$$\gamma = \beta^x1 + \beta^x2 \dots \dots \epsilon \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

The empirical outcomes of the first regression model are reported in Table 4.8 The approximate value of the (R-squared) coefficient shows that the variance of the independent variable values (Agri Islamic Loan) simultaneously explains the variation of the dependent variable (Agri profit) to a degree of 0.8600, 86 percent of which. For this production, the coefficient value of Agri Islamic profit (2.92) is a good effect, the likelihood increases with a standard value of 0.5 which is (0.2562) which is important. Agri-Islamic loan with a coefficient of (0.010000) is a 1% increase (0.01) in the contribution of agribusiness loans. The result of the Agri-Islamic loan probability is (0.0480) which is good. Durbin Watson Show the

2.185 which show greater than 2 which show no auto-correlation. Adjusted R-square (0.780000), Probability (F-stat) which is 0.000. These all values shows a significant result.

B. DEPENDENT VARIABLE: SMEPROFIT

Method: Least Squares

Date: 06/24/20 Time: 01:40

Sample (adjusted): 2 33

Included observations: 32 after adjustments

Variable	Coefficien	Std.	t-	Prob.
Cr	t	Error	Statistic	
C	0.005	6.10E	8.19E+1	0
SMEPROFIT(-1)	-5.03E-15	1.66E	-	0.0051
SMEISLAMLOA		-15	3.026886	
N	0.0506	1.10E	4.60E+1	0.0476
		-16	4	
R-squared	0.78	Mean dependent var	2.90817	5
Adjusted R-squared	0.69	S.D. dependent var	0.43046	
S.E. of regression	4.67E-15	Sum squared resid	6.33E-	28
F-statistic	1.32E+29	Durbin-Watson stat	2.32021	2
Prob (F-statistic)	0.000000			

TABLE 3: Estimated parameters of the simple linear regression model by using the method of least squares.

Estimated parameters of the multiple linear regression models by using the method of least squares following equation are used:

$$\text{SME Profit} = \alpha + (\text{SME Profit})_{t-1} + \text{Islamic finance}$$

The estimated value of the coefficient of (R-squared) reveals that the simultaneous variation of the values of the independent variables (SMEs Islamic loan) explains the variation of dependent variable (SMEs profit) to an extent of 0.7800 which 78%. The coefficient value of SMEs profit is (-5.03E-15) have negative impact which is not good effect for this output and also SMEs profit T Statistic also have the negative value (-3.026886), Probability increase with the standard value of 0.5 which is (0.0051). SMEs loan which coefficient is (0.050600) means 5% increase (0.05) contribution in SMEs loan and T Statistic (4.60E+14), SMEs Islamic loan probability result is (0.0476) which is valid. Durbin Watson statistics show the result value (2.320212) that shows no auto-correlation. Adjusted R-square (0.690000), Probability (F-statistic) which is

0.000. These all of the valve show the significant result.

It was examined from the previous literature that the many researchers has done the regression analysis least square The Islamic banking performance in Indonesia with different parameters they also have significant value and stationary data (Ayadi & Ellouze, 2013 Yadarudin, 2012 Hakimi et al, 2015; Bello & Isola, 2014).

VIII. CONCLUSION

The quantitative analysis of research study comprehensively concludes the most important points of topics analyzed and discussed based on research objectives. The study aimed to investigate the effect of Islamic finance on Agribusiness and the growth of small and medium-sized enterprises on the profitability of the different Islamic banking sectors used by Islamic banks. This Quantitative analysis focuses on secondary data, systematically collected data from 2008 to 2019 to respond to research issues from secondary sources. In addition the SPSS& EVIEWS program has been used for data processing. The research consists of one research issue, three objectives and two hypotheses.

The findings of this paper show the Islamic mode suited to agribusiness and small and medium-sized enterprises for lending. AGRI profit and SMEs Performing financing has a significant Islamic finance growth for agribusiness and Islamic finance growth for SMEs.

Islamic banking Shariah rules apply which positive impact that interest rate does not affect agricultural financing. The existence of Islamic banks is needed by the people of Pakistan, especially those with SMEs economies such in the agricultural sector.

Therefore, Funding must therefore be considered and given to fully support the middle and small communities so that they can have easy access to business capital. This research encourages Islamic banking practitioners to pay more attention to Islamic bank financing to farmers in Pakistan. This finding recommends enhancing the potential of Islamic financing tools in the agricultural sector and strengthening the instruments of Islamic finance policy. It was concluded from the outcome that funding is provided by Islamic Bank to Agribusiness plays an important role in Oder in improving the performance of Islamic financing.

Islamic finance impact on the welfare of the population. It has been shown that increased funding has been channeled to the Agribusiness and SMEs. The success of agriculture and SMEs had a major positive effect on welfare. Improved asset and benefit efficiency would make it easier for all sectors to achieve better profit. The suggestion is that governments should proactively develop progressive policies and create an enabling environment that promotes the growth of agribusiness and small and medium-sized enterprises by expanding innovative sources of funding, such as Islamic finance. Appropriate policies resources must be deliberately focused on the development of capital methods for the enforcement of contracts, research and the generation and management of quality data. Well-facilitated Agribusiness and small and medium-sized enterprises can be transformed into reliable corporate entities that help to address some of the inefficiencies experienced by governments of developing countries in their direction in the provision of social services.

IX. RECOMMENDATION

Nowadays agriculture had several beneficial advantages. Muhammad Ridhwan Ab. Aziz (2012) pointed out in his academic discourse that there are at least four advantages and contributions of agriculture namely: 1) it played a great role in developing human civilization since the beginning of human knowledge on cultivation and live-stocking until now, 2) it provides foods, clothing, shelter and many other basic needs that every human being needs, 3) it helps developing the economy development through *zakat* collection (collected from the rich to be given to the poor) and solving unemployment issues, and 4) it allows Muslims to perform several forms of religious worships (e.g. Paying *zakat*, perform *Eid al-Adha's* sacrifice). Even though there are some risks within the field, its advantages are far greater and more beneficial. However, due to its increasing demand, developing countries are formulating policies to make it more employable and economic-oriented and bring positive results for country's GDP (Gross Domestic Product). Following recommendations have been found in this research study:

- The government should develop the effective policies that will contribute to the growth of agribusiness and help to improve the economy through Islamic finance and small (SMEs).

- This research finding recommends improving the competency of Islamic finance tools in the agriculture sector as well as enhancing Islamic financing policy instruments.
- The suggestion that governments should proactively develop progressive policies and build an enabling environment through expanding creative sources of funding such as Islamic finance, promotes the growth of agribusiness and small and medium-sized enterprises.

X. RESEARCH LIMITATION

The purpose of this research was to investigate the contribution of Islamic finance with an emphasis on experimental study to the economic growth of agribusiness and SMEs. Theoretical and empirical research is required however as Islamic banking is relatively new to the banking industry. Some areas where further research is needed are as follows:

- i. Compared to conventional banking, how effective is Islamic banking and how can Islamic banks improve their effectiveness?
- ii. A comparative analysis on the instruments they use among Islamic banks in different countries?
- iii. How can Islamic banks solve or mitigate asymmetric knowledge, moral risk and adverse choice issues?

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